

AstroSat detection of long-duration X-ray superflares on EQ Peg

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Abstract

We present preliminary results of the study of three large long-duration flares detected on the active M-dwarf binary EQ Peg using the Soft X-ray Telescope of the *AstroSat* observatory. The peak X-ray luminosities of the flares in the 0.3–7 keV band are found to be $\sim 4\text{--}10 \times 10^{30}$ erg s⁻¹. Spectral analysis indicates that the corona of EQ Peg has three dominant temperatures, with the first two plasma temperatures remaining constant during all the flares and the post-flare observation at ~ 3 and ~ 11 MK. The flare temperature peaked at 56, 40, and 31 MK, which are 2.5, 1.8, and 1.4 times the minimum value. The peak emission measures are found to be $1.16\text{--}5.64 \times 10^{53}$ cm⁻³, whereas the elemental abundances peaked at 0.7–1.2 times the solar abundances. Using quasi-static loop modeling, we estimated the loop lengths for all the flares to be of the order of 10^{11} cm. The estimated energies of all three flares are $> 10^{33\text{--}35}$ erg which put them in the category of superflare. Our study indicates that all three flares on EQ Peg are associated with coronal mass ejections (CMEs). We estimated the CME mass and outward velocity of the CME are of the order of 10^{19} g and $\sim 5800\text{--}6500$ km s⁻¹, respectively. All three superflares are also found to be the longest duration flares ever observed on EQ Peg.

1 Introduction

Flares are the most extreme evidence of magnetic activity in solar/stellar atmospheres. Typical energies of the solar flares are within $10^{29\text{--}32}$ erg, whereas the stellar flares with energies $10^{33\text{--}38}$ erg are generally termed as ‘superflares’ (Schaefer *et al.*, 2000; Shibayama *et al.*, 2013). Although thousands of superflares have been observed to date in UV and optical bands (Tu *et al.*, 2020), X-ray superflare observations are still very few (see Karmakar *et al.*, 2017, and references therein). Most of the host stars showing X-ray superflares are found to be either M-dwarfs or binary or multiple star systems with an M-dwarf component. Active dwarfs of spectral types M0–M4 are known to be strong coronal X-ray sources with X-ray luminosities often close to the saturation limit of $L_X/L_{bol} \sim 10^{-3.3}$ (Fleming *et al.*, 1993; Pizzolato *et al.*, 2003). These stars show frequent and strong flaring activities during which the star’s total X-ray luminosity increases by more than two orders of magnitude (e.g. Favata *et al.*, 2000; Schmitt *et al.*, 2008).

The active M dwarf binary EQ Peg (BD+19 5116, GJ 896) has shown frequent and large flaring activities across the electromagnetic spectrum. With an age of 950 Myr (Parsamyan, 1995), the visual binary system EQ Peg is located at a distance of 6.260 ± 0.003 pc (Bailer-Jones *et al.*, 2018). The system consists of an M3.5 primary (EQ Peg A) and an M4.5 secondary (EQ Peg B), separated by an angular separation of $5''.8$ (Liefke *et al.*, 2008). With V magnitudes of 10.35 and 12.4, both the primary and secondary components are well-known optical flare stars (Pettersen, 1976; Lacy *et al.*, 1976). Using SuperWASP transit survey data, a photometric period of EQ Peg has been derived to be 1.0664 day (Norton *et al.*, 2007). The EQ Peg system is a strong X-ray and extreme ultraviolet

(EUV) source with several recorded flares (Pallavicini *et al.*, 1990; Haisch *et al.*, 1987; Pallavicini *et al.*, 1986; Katsova *et al.*, 2002). Using the *XMM-Newton* observations, the A and B components were separated for the first time in X-rays (Robrade *et al.*, 2004). Although the two stars show considerable overlap owing to the instrumental point-spread function, it was possible to attribute about three-quarters of the overall X-ray flux to the A component (Robrade & Schmitt, 2005). The first X-ray observation that allowed an unambiguous spectral separation of the two binary components was done with *Chandra*/HETG (Liefke *et al.*, 2008). Morin *et al.* (2008) also found that the Zeeman Doppler imaging map of EQ Peg A had a strong magnetic field spot of 0.8 kG, while EQ Peg B had a strong spot of 1.2 kG.

In this paper, we presented our preliminary results on three superflares on the M-dwarf binary EQ Peg observed with the first Indian multi-wavelength space observatory *AstroSat*. The paper is structured as follows: the observations and the data reduction procedure are discussed in Section 2. Analysis and results from X-ray timing and spectral analysis are presented in Section 3. Finally, in Section 4, we have discussed our results and presented conclusions.

2 Observations and Data Reduction

EQ Peg was observed in an energy range of 0.3–7 keV using the Soft X-ray Telescope (SXT; Singh *et al.*, 2017) onboard *AstroSat* observatory, during 2019 October 21–23 (PI. Karmakar; ID: A07_094T01_9000003248). We used AS1SXTLeve12-1.4b pipeline software to process the level 1 data to produce level 2 clean event files for each or-

Figure 1: The *AstroSat*/SXT light curve of three consecutive flares on EQ Peg in the 0.3–7 keV energy range is shown. The temporal binning of the light curve is 200 s. The brown dashed lines show the exponential fit to the light curve of the individual flares, whereas the solid black line shows the resultant superimposed fit to all the flares. The ‘Pre-Flare’ and ‘Post-Flare’ segments have been marked with the blue shaded region.

bit of observation. The `sxtevtmerger` tool¹ has been used to merge the event files corresponding to each orbit into a single clean event file for further analysis. The images, light curves, and spectra are extracted using the `FTOOLS` task `xselect V2.4k`, which has been provided as a part of the latest `heasoft` version 6.28. We have carried out the spectral analysis in an energy range of 0.3–7 keV using the `xspec` package, version 12.11.1 (Arnaud, 1996). In our analysis, we have adopted the solar photospheric abundances (Z_{\odot}) from Anders & Grevesse (1989), whereas we used the cross-sections obtained by Morrison & McCammon (1983) to model the equivalent hydrogen column density N_{H} .

3 Analysis and Results

3.1 X-Ray Light Curves

The *AstroSat*/SXT observation of the source began at HJD = 2458778.06559 day (=T0). We have detected three consecutive flaring events (F1, F2, F3) during the observation. The background-subtracted X-ray light curve of EQ Peg in the 0.3–7 keV energy range is shown in Figure 1. The light curve shows an almost constant pre-flare phase for 20 ks from the start of the observation with a median initial count rate of ~ 0.5 count s^{-1} . Due to the periodic gap in the data due to *AstroSat* orbits, the rising phase of the flare F1 is not observed and is interpolated with a blue dot-dashed line. The first flare (F1) survived up to around T0+58 ks, reaching a peak SXT count rate of ~ 1.6 count s^{-1} . The second flare (F2) starts

right after the flare F1 and decays until T0+84 ks. The flare F2 is found to have a projected peak count rate of ~ 1.3 count s^{-1} . The third flare (F3) is also found to be started just after the flare F2 and reaches a peak count rate of ~ 1 count s^{-1} . The flare F3 lasts for 38 ks until \sim T0+120 ks. The brown dashed lines in Figure 1 show the exponential rise and decay of each flare. At the same time, the superposition of decay and rise of two consecutive flares are shown with the solid black line. The e-folding rise times (τ_r) of the flares F2 and F3 are derived to be 6.0 ± 0.8 and 6.0 ± 0.7 ks, respectively, whereas the respective e-folding decay times (τ_d) for flares F1, F2, and F3 are derived to be 20.2 ± 1.8 , 4.7 ± 0.8 , 3.4 ± 0.3 ks.

3.2 Spectral Analysis

This section describes the X-ray spectral analysis of EQ Peg using *AstroSat*/SXT data. We performed time-resolved spectroscopy to trace the changes in the spectral parameters during the observation. Considering the data gap in the SXT light curve, in order to have approximately equal total counts in all the segments, we have divided the SXT light curves into fourteen segments, which include two segments of ‘Pre-Flare’, five segments of flare F1, three segments of flare F2, three segments of flare F3, and one ‘Post-Flare’ segment. All the time-resolved spectra are shown in Figure 2.

For the ~ 150 ks of *AstroSat* observation of EQ Peg, no distinct quiescent state was observed. For preliminary analysis, therefore, as a starting point, we chose the ‘Post-Flare’ segment as the ‘proxy’ of the quiescent phase due to its lowest mean count rate. The coronal parameters of the ‘Post-Flare’ phase were derived by fitting the spectrum with single (1-T),

¹https://www.tifr.res.in/astro_sat_sxt/dataanalysis.html

Figure 2: The time-resolved *AstroSat*/SXT spectra are shown. Different colours indicate spectra of different time segments as mentioned in Section 3.2.

two (2-T), and three (3-T) temperatures Astrophysical Plasma Emission Code (APEC; see Smith *et al.*, 2001) as implemented for collisionally ionized plasma. A 3-T plasma model with sub-solar abundances is found to have the best fit for the Post-Flare segment. Further addition of temperature component does not improve the χ^2 values of the fitting. The best-fit temperatures are derived to be 0.25 ± 0.02 , 0.98 ± 0.06 , and >2.45 keV for the Post-Flare segment. The global abundances (Z) were derived to be $0.486 \pm 0.024 Z_{\odot}$. The unabsorbed X-ray Luminosity (L_X) in the 0.3–7 keV range was calculated to be 2.5×10^{30} erg s^{-1} using the CFLUX task.

Spectra corresponding to all the segments during the pre-Flare and flaring events were extracted and fitted with 1-T, 2-T, and 3-T plasma models. Among these three models, the 3-T plasma model was acceptable for fitting the spectra of all the segments of flares. Since N_H was found to be constant (within 1σ uncertainty level), we fixed N_H to its average value of 2.32×10^{20} atoms cm^{-2} . The first two temperatures and corresponding emission measures (EMs) were constant within the 1σ uncertainty level. The average values of the first two temperatures over all the segments are 0.24 ± 0.04 and 0.95 ± 0.08 keV, whereas the corresponding EMs are derived to be $6.98 \pm 0.07 \times 10^{52}$ and $6.04 \pm 0.08 \times 10^{52}$ cm^{-3} , respectively. These two temperatures and the EMs are found to be similar to those of the first two temperatures of the Post-Flare phase. Therefore, we fixed the first two temperatures and corresponding EMs at the average values for the further spectral fitting of the flare segments. Only the third temperature (kT_3) and corresponding EM (EM_3) are allowed to vary while fitting the flaring segments. The third components are also identified as the flare components. The abundance, kT_3 , EM_3 , and L_X were found to vary during the

flares. The peak values of abundances for flares F1, F2, and F3 were derived to be 1.11 ± 0.11 , 1.19 ± 0.08 , and $0.73 \pm 0.04 Z_{\odot}$, respectively, which were 2.3, 2.5, and 1.5 times that of the post-flaring region. The derived peak flare temperatures for F1, F2, and F3 are 2.5, 1.8, and 1.4 times the lowest observed third thermal component. The EM_3 values followed the flare light curve and peaked at a value of 5.64×10^{53} , 2.25×10^{53} , and 1.16×10^{53} cm^{-3} for flares F1, F2, and F3, which are approximately 7, 3, and 1.5 times that of the Post-Flare region, respectively. The peak values of L_X in the 0.3–7 keV energy band during flares F1, F2, and F3 are derived to be $10^{31.01 \pm 0.02}$, $10^{30.89 \pm 0.02}$, and $10^{30.58 \pm 0.02}$ erg s^{-1} . This shows that the flares F1, F2, and F3 are approximately 4, 3, and 1.5 times as luminous as that of the Post-Flare regions.

4 Discussion and Conclusions

In order to infer the physical size and structure of the spatially unresolved stellar flares, we have used the flare loop model based on quasi-static radiative and conductive cooling during the decay (van den Oord & Mewe, 1989). According to this model the ratio of the radiative cooling time (τ_{rad}) and the conductive cooling time (τ_{cond}) remains constant during decay phase of the flare. Assuming the shape of the flaring loops to be semicircular with a constant cross-section throughout the flare, the quasi-static decay time scale can be determined using Equation 26 of van den Oord & Mewe (1989) as

$$EM(t) = EM(t_0) \left(1 + \frac{t - t_0}{3\tau_{qs,EM}} \right)^{-26/7} \quad (1)$$

$$kT(t) = kT(t_0) \left(1 + \frac{t - t_0}{3\tau_{qs,kT}}\right)^{-8/7} \quad (2)$$

where t_0 is an arbitrary initial epoch and $\tau_{qs,EM}$ and $\tau_{qs,kT}$ are the quasi-static cooling timescales. In the present case, t_0 is considered as the flare peak time of each flare. The emission measure $EM(t)$ and temperature $kT(t)$ are the time-dependent parameters. For all three flares F1, F2, and F3, we confirm that both the time scales are indeed the same (within the errors), i.e., $\tau_{qs,EM} \approx \tau_{qs,kT}$. Therefore, in the following analysis, we use $\tau_{qs,EM}$ as the cooling timescale ($= \tau_{qs}$) for all three flares, since it is better constrained than $\tau_{qs,kT}$. Using the fitted values of τ_{qs} , we derived the flare loop length (L) using the following equation of the quasi-static cooling model (van den Oord & Mewe, 1989; Tsuboi *et al.*, 2000),

$$L \text{ (cm)} = R_{\odot} \left(\frac{\tau_{qs}}{10 \text{ ks}}\right) \left(\frac{kT(t_0)}{\text{keV}}\right)^{7/8} \quad (3)$$

The preliminary results suggest that the flaring loop lengths for all three flares are of the order of 10^{11} cm, whereas the density of the flaring loops is on the order of 10^{11} cm $^{-3}$. The maximum pressure (p) in the loop at the flare peak can be estimated using the relation $p = 2n_e k T_{\text{max}}$, which suggests the maximum pressure p for flares is of the order of 10^3 dyne cm $^{-2}$. Therefore, the flaring loop volume (V) and the minimum magnetic field (B) to confine the flaring plasma are estimated to be of the order of 10^{31} cm 3 and 10^2 G, respectively. The peak X-ray luminosities of the flares in the 0.3–7 keV band are found to be $\sim 4\text{--}10 \times 10^{30}$ erg s $^{-1}$. All three flares are found to emit large flare energies ($> 10^{33\text{--}35}$ erg) and hence can be classified as ‘superflares’.

Using the empirical relationships of Aarnio *et al.* (2012) and Drake *et al.* (2013) between the solar flare X-ray energy and its associated CME mass, we have estimated the mass of the associated CME for each flare. The CME masses for all three flares are estimated to be of the order of 10^{19} g. The mean outward velocities of the associated CMEs on EQ Peg corresponding to the long-duration flares F1, F2, and F3 are estimated to be ~ 6486 , ~ 5668 , and ~ 5818 km s $^{-1}$, respectively.

Thus with *AstroSat*/SXT instrument we have analysed three consecutive superflares on EQ Peg. All three superflares are also found to be the longest duration flares ever observed on EQ Peg. Detailed study of the superflares will be presented elsewhere (Karmakar *et al.* 2021).

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